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MArinE Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management

D6.4

Report on the ML
processed through
mechanical recycling for
hard to recycle plastics
and organic wastes

10/03/2025

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Authoring & Approval

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Executive Summary

The present document refers to the results of task 6.4 “Hard to recycle plastics and organic wastes”. The task aimed at providing a new life to a wide array of plastics, not covered by thermal treatment, and organic material retrieved in the coastal areas in line with a circular economy and sustainable waste management concept. It highlights a mix of bottom up marine litter hand picking removal activities performed in the lagoon of Venice by VLPF with the participation of citizens and volunteers along with advanced mechanical proprietary processing of Gees Recycling. The latter was able to turn the collected marine litter (mainly HDPP and Fiber Reinforced Plastic) into secondary raw material feed stocking the production of a set of ML derived marketable items. Finally, the whole process from the location of origin of the litter to the end product was verified and tracked through the MAELSTROM app tracking function.

The ML was delivered from Venice to Gees Recycling plant in Aviano (Regularly authorized by Region Friuli Venezia Giulia for R3 and R13 waste recycling). The ML was further sorted according to size and other characteristics, then shredded in a double-shaft WRS 80 kw machine. The material collected, in particular End of Life (EOL) Boats, was preprocessed for metal recovery through a magnetic belt for ferrous and induction roll for non-ferrous metals provided by suitable third companies. The shredded waste was further size reduced in a rotary blade mill. Granulates were then packed identified by RFID tags and with all parameters data logged and stored. The granulates were then processed in the Gees Recycling panel production plant, where they were blended with additives and colorant, press-molded at high pressure and temperature (150 C) to sterilize the material and transform it mainly in panels. All production parameters and telemetries were logged, stored and made available for sharing in the MAELSTROM TRACKING PORTAL (T6.1)

Within this context, the report highlights the innovative integration of organic biomass and recycled marine litter to create sustainable, market-ready materials. Through the collaboration of civil society organizations and scientific partners, hard-to-recycle plastics and organic waste, such as shell residues and blue crab chitin, have been successfully blended to develop durable, eco-friendly products. These materials demonstrate potential for future applications in sectors such as outdoor furniture, promoting circular economy principles while offering environmentally responsible alternatives to conventional plastic-based products.

This report is intended to serve the purpose of being a guiding showcase document rich of self-explanatory images that shed lights and detail efforts carried out to turn

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hard to recycle and organic litter, with the involvement of civil society-based organizations, into new products ready for market or marketable in the future.

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Acronyms

CBBs Chemical Building Blocks

CONAI Consorzio Nazionale Rifiuti Imballaggio (National Consortium for Packaging Waste)

ECOPNEUS Eco Pneumatic (Eco tyre consortium)

EOL End of Life

FIBC Flexible Intermediate Bulk Containers (commonly known as BigBags)

FRP Fiber Reinforced Plastic

GEES Green Energy and Environmental Sustainability

GPP Green Public Procurement

Gri.Ma.Mo System for energy and vibration data logging

HCl Hydrogen Chloride

HCL Hydrochloric Acid

HDPE High Density Polyethylene

HDPP High-Density Polypropylene

MFI Melt Flow Index

ML Marine Litter

MPa Megapascal

OCBBs Organic Chemical Building Blocks

RFG Reinforced Fiber Glass

RFID Radio Frequency Identification

RFM Recycling of Flexible Materials

R-PMMA Recycled Poly(methyl methacrylate)

SEM Scanning Electron Microscope

TGA Thermogravimetric Analysis

TRL Technology Readiness Levels

UV Ultra Violet

VERITAS Venice Municipality Waste Management Authority

WRS Waste Recycling Systems

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1. MAELSTROM Project

MAELSTROM is a project funded under the Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. MAELSTROM strives to provide answers and diversified solutions to the complex issues regarding the removal and sustainable treatment of marine litter legacy.

MAELSTROM contemplates the integration of complementary technologies for marine litter removal in different European coastal ecosystems, compounded with full-fledged circular economy and societal oriented solutions. In particular, the project (i) outlines a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort marine litter; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of marine litter removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort and recycle all types of collected marine litter into valuable raw materials for future marketisation; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions while providing a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) raises social awareness about the marine litter issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for marine litter removal within and outside the EU.

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2. MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of the following members:

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	Deltares	Deltares	Frans BUSCHMAN Frans.Buschman@deltares.nl
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	The International Sustainable Development Initiatives	ISDI	Manuel SCARPA m.scarpa@isdigroup.com
	Gees Recycling Srl	GEES	Giorgio BETTETO geesretracking@gmail.com
	Venice Lagoon Plastic Free	VLPF	Davide POLETTO d.poletto@plasticfreevenice.org
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	MAKEEN	MAKEEN	Anders BJORN ABJ@makeenenergy.com
	National Center for Scientific Research	CNRS	Marc GOUTTEFARDE marc.gouttefarde@lirmm.fr

Table 1 Partner's list and abbreviations.

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3. Marine Litter Circular Value Chain

MAELSTROM's marine litter removal and recycling provides a new life to a wide array of plastics and composites (not covered by thermal treatment) and organic material retrieved in the coastal areas in line with a circular economy concept and sustainable waste management principles, for a recycling process whose key phases are described as it follows and outlined in the below flowchart and infographics:

- **Characterize, track and analyze** - The collected debris were characterized by their polymer composition, location and typology of items found. They were tracked using the Maelstrom APP and Portal , and analysed – in compliance with the Italian laws and regulations
- **Sort & Transform** – the removed debris were sorted according to their typology, turned into secondary raw material, blended with other components to achieve a full regeneration of its chemical composition to be fit for market access.
- **Marketize** - dedicated exploitation and scoping activities were designed to facilitate the marketization of recycled and regenerated materials to enter in the market chain as end products.

Figure 1 Illustrated scheme on MAELSTROM's key phases -D6.4 main contents are highlighted in red square.

Figure 2 Flowchart of recycling process of Hard to Recycle ML

3.1 The Marine Litter Tracking Service with MAELSTROM APP

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Maelstrom App and Portal provides the now completed “Tracking” service, that permits to follow the waste transport and recycling throughout the whole circular process.

The tracking service is integrated into the Maelstrom Web Portal to accommodate specific work requirements, including the entry of document numbers, references, and the selection of multiple items, all of which can be efficiently managed via a portable computer or tablet. Access to the portal is restricted to authorized users only and is available at www.maelstrom.way.to.it.

The operation of the app is simple and straightforward. It has been further adapted and is customizable, enabling it to track both manned activities—through the involvement of citizens and grassroots organizations—and automated collection activities using cleanup robots. This is achieved in a systematic, step-by-step manner:

Figure 3 First step – create a specific chosen cleanup action

The screenshot displays the 'Update Cleanup Items' interface. The form contains the following fields:

- Luogo del Cleanup:** Venezia Campo test
- Data inizio:** 13/1/2021
- Data fine:** 13/1/2021
- Lat:** 45.474877
- Long:** 12.300788
- Team leader:** Davide x banche
- Participant Number:** 5

Image upload sections include:

- Foto dopo:** Trascina i file qui ...
- Foto prima:** Campo test.jpg (36.32 KB)

Buttons at the bottom of the form include: Annulla, Salva, Salva, Close without saving, Save and Close, and Close.

Below the form is the 'Cleanup Items' table:

ID	Cleanup ID	Cleanup Waste Type	Tipo rifiuto	dimensioni sacco	weight
196	Venezia Campo test	Nets, Ropes, Fishing Boats	Mixed	{nessun valore}	255.00
197	Venezia Campo test	Wood processed and furniture	Mixed	70	230.00
198	Venezia Campo test	Macrolitter Boats and parts	Recyclable	50	120.00

Figure 4 Second step: Select the items to be tracked

Figure 5 Third step – Click on green “Tracking” button , pop-up window will appear

Figure 6 Fourth step – Compile tracking data, with consignee of the waste, date and time, location and official document number

Due to variations in waste handling regulations across different countries, it was decided to use "generic" terms that can be customized and "localized" through the "Translate" function of the portal. The tracking system monitors waste throughout its entire circular process. In the pop-up window, users can add any number of tracking steps to trace the lifecycle of the waste. To complete the process, simply click the blue "Track" button.

The "Tracking" Menu collects all the historical trackings performed.

Figure 7 MAELSTROM's App. Display of all historical trackings performed.

Here is possible to select the required trackings, acting on any of the data fields in single or multiple parameters.

Figure 8 MAELSTROM'S App. Selection of required trackings through single or multiple parametres

Tracking data may be exported in different formats ready for integration or data processing:

Table 2 MAELSTROM'S App. Tracking data exported into an excel table

The app is reliable and user-friendly. The web-based portal is accessible from any device with online capabilities. Logs of user operations are securely stored and can be retrieved to ensure accountability in the functioning of the Maelstrom App and Portal.

Here below are reported the cleanups and tracking activities:

ID	Cleanup ID	Cleanup Waste Type	Waste Type	Pack dimension	Weight	Location Longitude	Location Latitude	Data
	303 Sacca Fisola Venezia	Tyres and wheels	Recyclable		70	300 45,4252	12,31013	21/09/23
	304 Sacca Fisola Venezia	FRP-Wood boat and parts	Recyclable		70	1255		
	311 Sottomarina	Nets , Ropes , Fishing floaters	Mixed		70	73,6 45.169814	12.327484	22/10/22
	312 Sottomarina	Nets , Ropes , Fishing floaters	Recyclable		70	63,8		
ID	Cleanup ID	Cleanup Waste Type	Waste Type	Pack dimension	Weight			
	317 Punta San Giuliano	FRP-Wood boat and parts	Recyclable		70	1680 45.46588	12,28203	02/12/22
	318 Punta San Giuliano	Nets , Ropes , Fishing floaters	Recyclable		70	198		
ID	Cleanup ID	Cleanup Waste Type	Waste Type	Pack dimension	Weight			
	319 Pellestrina	Nets , Ropes , Fishing floaters	Recyclable		60	165 45.282532	12.304961	15/12/22

Table 3 Reporting of the performed cleanups and tracking activities

We successfully recycled significant quantities of marine litter while keeping the tracking system fully operational. This system clearly demonstrates the source and original location of the collected waste.

ID	Cleanup ID	Cleanup Waste Type	Waste Type	Pack dimension	Weight
	317 Punta San Giuliano	FRP-Wood boat and parts	Recyclable		70 1680
	318 Punta San Giuliano	Nets , Ropes , Fishing floaters	Recyclable		70 198

Table 4 Detailed reporting of cleanups with source and original location of the collected waste

ID 317

Figure 9: Examples of different litter items recovered and tracked: the tracking system works with a fine-tuning option according to different levels of required precision.

For industrial recycling operations, we make use of units ranging from 100 kg to 1,000 kg. In MAELSTROM, we planned to fully utilize citizen-driven cleanup operations organized by VLPF to supply GEES with the entire feedstock of hard-to-recycle plastic litter for processing.

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It must be noted that packaging-related wastes and tires collected during the cleanup were not processed by GEES. According to Italian law, these materials must be handled by specifically authorized facilities and operators within mandatory national industrial consortia.

The outcomes of these operations are documented, detailing the quantity of litter collected and its intermediate to final destinations.

Figure 10 Quantity and typology of litter collected

4. The “hard to recycle plastics “Marine Litter processed in Gees Recycling

Since the start of the project, Gees recycling committed to develop a viable way to obtain marketable products from marine litter net of specific marine litter items. As aforementioned the Italian waste management regulations provide that specific waste, case in point packaging waste, car and truck tyres and other household waste are subject to CONAI (Consorzio Nazionale Rifiuti Imballaggio) and ECOPNEUS (tyre consortium), state financed consortia for the collection and recycle/disposal of the above categories of waste. Gees Recycling is an authorized waste treatment recycler, not affiliated neither to CONAI nor to ECOPNEUS. For this reason it can't receive or process those waste, whose treatment is however already provided by traditional recycling processes.

Figure 11 ML's debris packed respectively in yellow (recyclable) and black (non-recyclable) bags.

In the above pictures, taken during the first Maelstrom cleanup in May 2021 organised by VLPF and ISDI, you can notice that the ML is packed in bags of different color, namely yellow and black for recyclable and non-recyclable debris accordingly. Both of them were delivered to VERITAS, Venice municipality waste management authority. The white big bag contains other type of waste, hard to recycle- to be delivered to GEES RECYCLING treatment plant. It is also noticeable the marine litter tracking function in action via Maelstrom APP.

Marine Litter, in particular macroplastics, are composed by significant quantities of different materials and polymers, that are not of pertinence of CONAI and Ecopneus, and that would most likely end in landfill or burnt. This is the case of synthetic ropes and RFG that Gees recycling plant attempted to treat.

Figure 12 First cleanup – May 2021

The above picture provides an example of the wide array of ML such as ropes and nets – mostly made of a mix of Polyester, Polypropylene and PA6 polymers, along with pieces of FRP from broken recreational boats left abandoned in nature.

Figure 13 Pellestrina cleanup December 2021

During several cleanup campaigns from 2021 to 2024, VLPPF collected large quantities of buoys made of HDPE from mussels farming stations, shell farms, and fishing nets stranded along the Venice shoreline. Massive sections of landing stages used by local public sea boats (vaporetti), constructed from extra-durable HDPE, were also picked up. These were cut into smaller pieces and delivered to TECNALIA for recycling.

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Furthermore, our efforts were bolstered by the ongoing cooperation with VLPF's permanent program, "Ghost Boats," which focuses on removing and processing end-of-life (EOL) boats abandoned in the lagoon and along the shorelines of Venice and its islands. We successfully retrieved and processed 31 EOL vessels, primarily recreational, at Gees Recycling facilities. These boats underwent pre-processing, including shredding and metal recovery, to become secondary raw feedstock. Additionally, unexpected items such as airplane tires were discovered and appropriately disposed of through VERITAS.

Macrolitter:

Figure 14 Most frequent ML macrolitter found in the seaside of Venice : Left nets, Center mussel socks , Right, small nets and floaters

Macrolitter:

Figure 15 Left) FRP abandoned boat; Right) Truck tyres collected by the seabed MAELSTROM robotic platform.

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4.1 Material characteristics and specific precautions

Under the current waste management regulations and Gees Recycling's authorized waste management provisions, there is a mandate to analyze marine litter. The analyses conducted on all marine litter received and processed confirmed compliance, classifying the materials as "Special –

RAPPORTO DI PROVA N°		2023 / 223	Dosson di Casier, 18/01/2023	
Spett.le GEES RECYCLING SRL VIA MONTE COLOMBERA, 22 33081 AVIANO (PN)				
Accettazione nr.: 6481 Campione: Plastiche raccolte - Progetto MAELSTROM 101 000 832 - Codice EER 170203 (Plastica)				
Data di campionamento: 17/12/2022 Luogo di campionamento: Comune di Venezia - Campalto (VE) Campionato da: Cliente Metodo di campionamento: * UNI 10802:2013 Data ricevimento: 19/12/2022 Data inizio analisi: 19/12/2022 Data fine analisi: 16/01/2023				
Parametro	Risultato	Inc. (s)	Unità di Misura	Metodo di Analisi
*Stato Fisico	Solido	-	-	UNI 10802:2013
pH	7,2		unità di pH	CNR IRSA 1 064 Vol 3 1985-APAT CNR IRSA 2060 Mar 29 2003
Residuo a 105°C	98,8		%	UNI EN 14346:2007 M&A
Commento al Rapporto di Prova N°		2023 / 223	Dosson di Casier, 18/01/2023	
CONCLUSIONI				
Spett.le GEES RECYCLING SRL VIA MONTE COLOMBERA, 22 33081 AVIANO (PN)				
Accettazione nr.: 6481 Campione: Plastiche raccolte - Progetto MAELSTROM 101 000 832 - Codice EER 170203 (Plastica)				
Data di campionamento: 17/12/2022 Luogo di campionamento: Comune di Venezia - Campalto (VE)				
VALUTAZIONI AI FINI DELLA CLASSIFICAZIONE DEL RIFIUTO I parametri analizzati sono stati scelti in base alla tipologia del rifiuto e alle indicazioni fornite dal produttore. Il codice EER è stato dichiarato dal produttore/identificatore del rifiuto ai sensi della Decisione Comen. 2014/955/UE, al sensi del D.Lgs. N. 152 del 3 aprile 2006, parte IV e successive modifiche ed integrazioni, ai sensi della Decisione del 18 dicembre 2014, N. 2014/955/UE, ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) N. 1357/2014 del 18 dicembre 2014 e del Regolamento (UE) N. 2019/1021 del 20 giugno 2019, ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) N.2016/1179 del 19 luglio 2016 recante modifica, ai fini dell'adeguamento al progresso tecnico e scientifico, del regolamento (CE) n. 1272/2008 e ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) 2017/997 dell'8 giugno 2017 che modifica l'allegato III della direttiva 2006/95/CE del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, tenuto conto della Delibera SNPA n. 105/2021 "Linee guida sulla classificazione dei rifiuti" approvata dal D.M. n.47 del 9 agosto 2021, il rifiuto in esame è classificabile come: • SPECIALE NON PERICOLOSO.				

Figure 16 Non-Hazardous waste reports

Fiberglass, especially in abandoned boats, has necessitated a specialized response from Gees Recycling. Recognizing the health risks associated with smaller fiberglass particles, GEES has implemented additional testing specifically to gauge the size of the fibers present in these materials. This measure is critical because fibers smaller

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than 6 micrometers are known to pose a cancer risk due to their potential to be inhaled and penetrate deep into lung tissue.

By conducting these specific tests for fiber size gauging, Gees Recycling aimed to ensure that no hazardous fibers are present in the boats they recycle. This careful scrutiny is part of the company's commitment to health and safety standards,

Commento al Rapporto di Prova N°
2023/ 222**Dossion di Casler, 18/01/2023**

CONCLUSIONI

Spett.le **GEES RECYCLING SRL**
VIA MONTE COLOMBERA, 22
33081 AVIANO (PN)

Accettazione nr.: **6480**

Campione: **Parti di vetroresina tratta da barca abbandonata - Progetto MAELSTROM 101 000 832 - Codice EER 170904 (Rifiuti misti dell'attività di costruzione e demolizione, diversi da quelli di cui alle voci 17 09 01, 17 09 02 e 17 09 03)**

Data di campionamento: 17/12/2022

Luogo di campionamento: Comune di Venezia - Campalto (VE)

CLASSIFICAZIONE ED ETICHETTATURA ARMONIZZATA DELLE FAV SECONDO IL REGOLAMENTO (UE) N. 1272/2008, ALLEGATO VI, COME MODIFICATO DAL REGOLAMENTO (UE) N. 790/2009

Visto che il tenore di ossidi alcalini e ossidi alcalino-terrosi ($\text{Na}_2\text{O}+\text{K}_2\text{O}+\text{CaO}+\text{MgO}+\text{BaO}$) risulta superiore al 18% e che il diametro medio geometrico ponderato rispetto alla lunghezza delle fibre, meno due errori geometrici standard, è superiore a **6 μm** , le fibre artificiali vetrose contenute si classificano come "LANE MINERALI NON CANCEROGENE".

VALUTAZIONI AI FINI DELLA CLASSIFICAZIONE DEL RIFIUTO

I parametri analizzati sono stati scelti in base alla tipologia del rifiuto e alle indicazioni fornite dal produttore.

Il codice EER è stato dichiarato dal produttore/detentore del rifiuto ai sensi della Decisione Comm. 2014/955/UE 18.12.2014 e del D.Lgs.152/06, parte IV e s.m.i.. Per i codici EER a specchio il laboratorio identifica le ultime due cifre del codice EER in base alla pericolosità/non pericolosità del campione analizzato.

In seguito alle indagini analitiche condotte sul campione, considerato il processo produttivo di provenienza del rifiuto, ai sensi del D.Lgs. N. 152 del 3 aprile 2006, parte IV e successive modifiche ed integrazioni, ai sensi della Decisione del 18 dicembre 2014, N. 2014/955/UE, ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) N. 1357/2014 del 18 dicembre 2014 e del Regolamento (UE) N. 2019/1021 del 20 giugno 2019, ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) N.2016/1179 del 19 luglio 2016 recante modifica, ai fini dell'adeguamento al progresso tecnico e scientifico, del regolamento (CE) n. 1272/2008 e ai sensi del Regolamento (UE) 2017/997 dell'8 giugno 2017 che modifica l'allegato III della direttiva 2008/98/CE del Parlamento europeo e del Consiglio, tenuto conto della Delibera SNPA n. 105/2021 "Linee guida sulla classificazione dei rifiuti" approvata dal D.M. n.47 del 9 agosto 2021, il rifiuto in esame è classificabile come:

- SPECIALE NON PERICOLOSO.

Figure 17 Test report conclusions

Gees specifically excluded wooden boats and their parts from their operations. This exclusion is due to the fact that Gees is not authorized to handle them, which do not fall within its operational scope. Additionally, there is a significant risk associated with

MAELSTROM

the degradation of these wooden materials. This is largely due to the probable presence of toxic paints and glues, which are still commonly used today despite their hazardous nature. GEES's decision to avoid treating wooden boats and components underlines its commitment to safety and compliance with regulatory standards, recognizing the specific risks associated with the materials used in these items.

4.2 Marine litter preparation for other project partners

Gees Recycling in collaboration with VLPF has also sorted and prepared ML to feed the thermo and mechanical plastic recycling of ML for TECNALIA (T6.1) whose purpose was to treat heterogenous and diversified highly representative plastic samples derived from the marine environment in terms of typology and degradation degree. This activity was carried out in order to determine the decrease of mechanical properties of plastics removed from the sea next to virgin material along with the Melt Flow Index MFI and the TGA: Thermogravimetric Analysis, to characterize materials with regard to their composition and degradation. The material provided undertook (i) Shredding/milling, (ii) Re-formulation of the milled material (by extrusion), and (iii) Re-processing of the obtained pellets (by injection or other thermoplastic techniques). The material was also sent to MAKEEN for low temperature pyrolysis treatment based on the "left over" of the ML collected after the segregation phase and the mechanical plastic recycling processes in Venice (Task 6.5). The remaining plastic litter collected by VLPF was treated by GEES Recycling by being cleaned, dried and shredded down to smaller sizes suitable for being transported and delivered to MAKEEN industrial power plant and to the experimental and portable pyrolysis prototype unit built by SINTOL within the frame of the EU marGnet project and adapted to MAELSTROM activities.

GEES RECYCLING S.r.L.
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 Tel. 0434654183
 e-mail: geesrecycling@gmail.com Pec: gees.recycling.srl@legalmail.it
 C.F./P.Iva 01678120930 - Rag. impresa 95657

Doc. di trasporto nr. **117/2022** del **21/06/2022**

Destinatario MAKEEN POWER A/S ALSVEJ21 DK-8940 RANDERS (SV)	Destinazione MAKEEN POWER A/S ALSVEJ21 DK-8940 RANDERS (SV)
---	---

Codice	Descrizione	Quantità
	CONTO CAMPIONI TEST PROVE MATERIALE LASTICO PER PROVE Progetto Maelstrom - H2020	3 nr

Plastic Material for tests - Maelstrom-H2020 Project

Inviato dal trasporto		Causale del trasporto		Data ricevuta del trasporto	
Destinatario		Campioni test in omaggio			
Nr. collo	Peso	Aspetto esteriore del bene	Peso	Data e ora inizio trasporto	Firma destinatario
3 NR	430 KG	BANCALE		21/06/2022 11:14	

Pag. 1

Figure 18 Transport document, October 2022 – 430 kg to MAKEEN Randers DK

GEES RECYCLING S.r.L.
 Via Monte Colomba n. 22 - 33081 Aviano (PN) - Italy
 Tel. 0434654183
 e-mail: geesrecycling@gmail.com Pec: gees.recycling.srl@legalmail.it
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Doc. di trasporto nr. **17/2023** del **13/02/2023**

Destinatario Sintol S.R.L. Via Vialardi D'Aras, 14 10121 Torino (TO) C.F./P.Iva 11291720016	Destinazione Makeen Power AS - Sintol S.R.L. Strada nuova per Caluso-Rocello 10014 Caluso (TO)
--	--

Codice	Descrizione	Quantità
	CAMPIONI DI MATERIALE COMPOSITO E PLASTICO PER PROVE DISTRUTTIVE N. 3 SCATOLE DI BANCALE RIF. PROGETTO MAELSTROM 10100832	1

Inviato dal trasporto		Causale del trasporto		Data ricevuta del trasporto	
Vettore PMO TRASPORTI & LOGISTICA		Campioni per prove distruttive			
Nr. collo	Peso	Aspetto esteriore del bene	Peso	Data e ora inizio trasporto	Firma destinatario
1	123 kg	BANCALE		13/02/2023 12:57	

Pag. 1

Figure 19 Transport document, February 2023 160 Kg to SINTOL Srl for MAKEEN

Figure 20 MAELSTROM's ML sent to Makeen/Sintol 1

GEES RECYCLING S.r.L.

Via Monte Columbara n. 22 - 31081 Aviano (PN) - Italy
Tel. 0434/644893
e-mail: geesrecycling@gmail.com Pcc: gees.recycling@irunegabmail.it
C.F./P.Iva 01678120930 Reg. imprese 95657

Doc. di trasporto
n. **90/2023** del **08/05/2023**

Destinatario TECNALIA IRUN Astondo Bidea, Edificio 700 E20305 Derio, Biscay Spain	Destinazione TECNALIA IRUN Call Gabiria 84 20305 Irun Spain
--	--

Cod. Fisc. ESG48975767

Codice	Descrizione	Quantità
Rif. progetto Maeltstrom 101000832 Cup B532004630006	Materiali plastici per prove distruttive	

Incaricato del trasporto Raben Sittam	Causale del trasporto Campioni per prove	Punto Cubicattiner	Firma incaricato del trasporto	Firma destinatario
N. coll 1	Peso 175	Aspetto anteriore del bene Cubicattiner	Data e ora inizio trasporto 08/05/2023 14:32	

Pag. 1

Figure 21 Transport document, May 2023 175 Kg to TECNALIA Irun E

4.3 Marine Litter processing with Gees RFM Mechanical recycling system

Figure 22 Gees Recycling processing line – panel output

The marine litter processed in GEES Recycling undertook the following steps:

1. **Shredding:** The first stage of processing marine litter is shredding, where a robust shredder systematically breaks down large debris into manageable pieces. This equipment is crucial for the preliminary reduction of waste volume, preparing the material for more refined processing. The shredded material is then transferred to a granulator that further processes these fragments through grids ranging in size from 6 to 15 mm, achieving a more uniform particle size.

Figure 23 Marine Litter on the conveyor for shredding

- 2. Granulation & Storage:** Following shredding, the granulated material undergoes a sorting process where it is meticulously identified and classified based on its source, type, size, color, and material composition. This granulate is then securely stored in Flexible Intermediate Bulk Containers (FIBC), commonly known as BigBags. This storage method facilitates organized inventory management and protects the quality of the material. The Gees recycling system integrates with the Maelstrom App and Portal, ensuring precise tracking and documentation of each FIBC's contents, location, and associated data. Furthermore, the impending installation of the Gri.Ma.Mo system in 2024 will enhance operational efficiency by logging the electrical consumption of the granulation line and performing vibration analysis, aiding in predictive maintenance and ensuring the longevity of the machinery.

Figure 24 Granulate, identified and tracked ready

- 3. Pre-mixing and Production:** The pre-mixing stage is mandatory for achieving a consistent and homogenous mixture. This process involves dry-mixing the granulated material to ensure uniform distribution of all components, which is critical for the quality and performance of the final product. After achieving a satisfactory mix, a small proportion (less than 5%) of a bonding agent is added during the wet-mixing phase. This agent helps in binding the particles together, enhancing the structural integrity of the manufactured product.

Figure 25 Granulate is mixed and homogenised

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1. **Panel Moulding:** In the final processing step, the homogenized mix is subjected to panel moulding. This is carried out in a heated press that applies both pressure and heat, polymerizing the litter mix and transforming it into rigid, dense panels. This process not only stabilizes the material but also ensures that the panels meet specific density and strength criteria, making them suitable for various applications in construction and other industries where sustainable building materials are valued.

Figure 26 Panel is formed, ready after Pression+Heat

Each of these steps is designed to optimize the recovery and reuse of marine litter, transforming environmental waste into valuable, circular and sustainable products.

4.4 Innovations and plant modifications required by ML processing

The marine litter feedstock must first be sorted and cleaned to remove any metal components that might be present, either mixed within various materials or embedded in items. This is especially common in end-of-life (EOL) boats as reinforcement components, or in plastic products such as handles for pails and hinges in furniture parts. These metals pose risks to both the processing machinery and the operators. To safely and efficiently process large quantities of material, specific equipment is required, such as mobile shredders equipped with dedicated metal separators.

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Additionally, cleaning is essential to address salt contamination, which commonly affects the traditional thermoplastic recycling of marine debris such as buoys. During the extrusion process, salt can generate HCl emissions, leading to corrosion risks and the release of noxious fumes. However, Gees' RFM process, which operates at a lower temperature (140°C compared to 240-280°C), is less susceptible to these issues and can tolerate higher levels of saltwater contamination. Mud and sand must also be removed, typically using a high-pressure water cleaner. At Gees, the water used for washing is collected by the industrial area's sewer system and treated accordingly. Mobile on-site operations require careful segregation, containment, and a dedicated water collection system.

Finally, specific modifications are necessary for the shredding line due to the abrasive nature of salt content, sand, and dust, which accelerate wear on cutting tools and shredders. Anti-wear treatments, such as nitride-oxide coating, are recommended. Similar challenges affect presses and molds, which face significant wear from high compression forces, up to 60 MPa, that can damage smooth surfaces if not adequately treated and protected.

4.5 Minor adjustments in the ML treatment process

The marine litter recycling process necessitated the identification of special bonding agents due to the unique conditions of the marine litter, such as salt contamination and the presence of sand and mud. After extensive testing, the enhanced bonding agent performed well, aligning with the processes used for standard feedstocks. A key finding from our tests is that the production of MAELSTROM-derived marine litter panels does not require a higher percentage of bonding agent compared to standard ones. We also evaluated various bonding agents and coatings, as detailed in section 6.1.2.

Regarding the time required for producing new items from marine litter, our tests indicated no significant differences compared to using standard feedstocks. Initially, longer polymerizing and curing times were required, but these were reduced in subsequent runs. Ultimately, the production times were comparable to those of standard panels.

In terms of emissions, we encountered no notable issues with either gaseous or liquid emissions. Consequently, the equipment installed for liquid emission containment and collection proved unnecessary. The hydrophilic nature of the bonding agent,

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which closely resembles the chemical structure of water, effectively absorbed any residual moisture present.

5. Marine Litter Production Outputs with Advanced Mechanical Recycling

Main scope of the project was to demonstrate that “Hard to recycle” ML may be transformed in useful materials and product using Gees patented mechanical recycling process, this chapter explain how we were able to succeed in this goal

The production tests were carried out in two modes for the production of panels as follows:

1. **Standard Size Panels:** Production of standard size panels, 2500 x 1250 mm, which are later cut and milled as typically used in building materials and furniture.
2. **Special Panels:** Production of special panels in various sizes for more complex operations, such as multilayer panels.

5.1 Test production runs standard panels

GEES conducted several production trials to transform waste mixtures into rigid panels, necessitating a controlled environment to ensure accurate results. A specific procedure was adopted to guarantee the performance:

- **Cleaning of the Production Line:** From FIBC-BigBags feeding to the mixing system.
- **Mould Preparation:** Moulds were prepared with anti-stick layers to facilitate removal of the panels.
- **Hydraulic Press Maintenance:** The hydraulic press was thoroughly cleaned and prepared before use.
- **Collection of Liquid Discharges:** Measures were in place to collect any possible liquid discharges, although none occurred.

These steps were critical in maintaining the integrity of the production trials and ensuring the quality of the produced panels. Each production runs was made from controlled and identified batches , each one worth of several panels made

- 5 different production tests were carried out:
 - 89.50 Dec. 2021 lot # 98 – Thickness 24 mm D. 1180

- 96.04 May 2022 lot # 162 – Thickness 20 mm D. 1056
- 98.01 January 2023 lot # 188 – Thickness 20 mm D. 1055
- 102.08 March 2023 lot # 230 – Thickness 18 mm D. 980
- 103.12 July 2024 lot 266 – Thickness 22 mm D. 1162

All the materials produced were then tested to evaluate the results according to a standard procedure:

1. Density calculation and verification of average deviation – tools : scale and caliber
2. Planarity verification- tools: rectified planarity bench , caliber
3. Surface roughness and porosity – tools : magnifying lens

Test results are reported here following:

- ○ 89.50 Dec. 2021 lot # 98 – Thickness 24 mm D. 1180
 - Density average : 1180 , lowest 1098 highest 1360 result out of tolerances
 - Planarity : Good : < 3 mm over 2500 mm lengthwise . < 2 mm broadwise
 - Surface roughness : Good , no evident porosity
- 96.04 May 2022 lot # 162 – Thickness 20 mm D. 1056
 - Density average : 1056 , lowest 1002 highest 1360 result out of tolerances
 - Planarity Good : < 3 mm over 2500 mm lengthwise . < 2 mm broadwise
 - Surface roughness : Good , no evident porosity
- 98.01 January 2023 lot # 188 – Thickness 20 mm D. 1055
 - Density average : 1055 , lowest 1001 highest 1260 result out of tolerances
 - Planarity : bad : > 5mm over 2500 mm lengthwise . > 3,5 mm broadwise
 - Surface roughness : bad, evident porosity
- 102.08 March 2023 lot # 230 – Thickness 18 mm D. 980
 - Density average : 980 , lowest 915 highest 1025 result in tolerances
 - Planarity : Good : < 3 mm over 2500 mm lengthwise . < 2 mm broadwise
 - Surface roughness : Good , no evident porosity
- 103.12 July 2024 lot 266 – Thickness 22 mm D. 1162
 - Density average : 1162 , lowest 10 highest 1185 result in tolerances

- Planarity : Very Good : < 1,5 mm over 2500 mm lengthwise . < 1 mm broadwise
- Surface roughness : very Good , no evident porosity , natural hydrophoby

103.12 is the best result and will be taken as base for further developments. More specific tests on this formulation will be done

103.12 was also submitted to a flame test; results were comforting since no flame propogation, low smoke and no droplets were observed.

Maelstrom	Production tests										
Test #	Period	Lot #	Thickness	Density avg	Density Max	Density min	In tolerance	Planarity	Surface	Edge	Grain
89.50	Dec 22	98	24	1180	1360	1094	No	>3	Good	AVG	Medium
96.04	May 22	162	20	1056	1260	1002	No	<3	Good	Good	Large
98.01	Jan 23	188	20	1055	1260	1001	No	>5	Bad	Bad	Magnum
102.08	Mar 23	230	18	980	915	1055	Yes	<3	Good	Bad	Normal
103.12	July 24	266	22	1162	1185	10501015	Yes	<3	Very Good	Good	Large

Table 5 Results of panel's production tests.

Examples:

Figure 27 Panel sample 96.04 LOT 162

Figure 28 Panel Sample 98.01 LOT 188

Figure 29 Panel Sample 102.08 LOT 230

Figure 30 Panel sample 103.12 LOT 266

The production trials conducted have successfully shown that it's possible to manufacture panels from marine litter that match the quality and performance of Gees Recycling's standard products. These panels, made from materials collected from the lagoon of Venice, retain their integrity without any compromise from contaminants or the corrosive effects of saltwater. The final products not only meet the necessary mechanical standards but also exhibit appealing aesthetic qualities.

5.2 Special panels and materials

Tests were conducted on innovative panels to explore ways to utilize marine litter, such as fishers' nets made of multipolymer compositions, without needing to shred or destroy the material. These tests aimed to develop panels with novel surface textures and appearances. Additionally, part of this endeavor involved collaboration with the LIFE GREEN COMPOSITE project. This partnership leveraged the R-PMMA technology developed by DELTA to produce a panel entirely from recycled materials.

Figure 31 MS 01/045 Panel made embedding fishinets in the mix of ML and fiberglass waste

The results of the tests on the specialized panels were visually appealing, but the process proved to be more complex and time-consuming compared to standard procedures. To produce these panels in larger quantities, additional engineering efforts will be necessary to refine and optimize the manufacturing process. This will ensure that while maintaining the aesthetic appeal, the production can become efficient enough to be viable on a larger scale.

MS 01/052

Figure 32 Panel with co-moulded mix of ML, roughly 40% nets, 30% mussels eq. remaining mixed plastics

MS03/062

Figure 33 Panel produced with small size particles from ML processing – partly taken from dust aspiration filters – Delamination problems right picture

MS04/022

Figure 34 Panel with marine litter and R-PMMA surface layer, joint project with Life Green Composite Promising product: the R-PMMA Surface give and excellent resistance to weather and UV

Figure 35 Panels made with: Maelstrom ML Recycled panel (103.12 SP) and ML surface layer with R-PMMA of Life Green composite project

6. Physical tests results on the standard panels

Several physical tests were performed on the produced panels, here below a comprehensive extract of the results obtained:

Type of Test :Flexural strength			
Norm EN ISO 178:2019			
Test	Flex Resistance Mpa	Elasticity Module Mpa	Strain at break %
# 01 Zag	9,8	1689	0,98
# 02 Catas	12,6	1500	1.0
# 03 Catas	10,2	1588	0,9

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Type of Test: Compression strength			
Norm EN ISO 604:2008			
Test	Maximum load N	Compression Resistance Mpa	
# 02 Catas	15494	35,9	
	15351	36,8	
	14573	36,4	
	15494	38,2	
	13847	33,9	
# 03 Catas	16252	37,2	
	16125	36,9	
	15851	37	
	15494	38,2	
	16351	37,4	
	16145	37,1	

∅

Rigonfiamento dopo 24 ore di immersione in acqua - Procedura CAtas			
Tipo di pannello dichiarato: Pannello vetroresina riciclata densità 1100			
Piano di taglio: Non allegato			
Dimensione delle provette: 50 mm x 50 mm			
Risultati di prova:			
Provetta n°	Spessore iniziale mm	Spessore finale mm	Rigonfiamento %
1	20,81	20,85	0,2
2	20,77	20,82	0,3
3	20,74	20,80	0,3
4	20,79	20,83	0,2
5	20,64	20,68	0,2
6	20,65	20,69	0,2
7	20,61	20,65	0,2
8	20,72	20,76	0,2
Valore medio			0,2
Scarto tipo			0,0
Coefficiente variazione			0,0
Note:			
- La prova è stata condotta seguendo le indicazioni della norma EN 317:1993, operando al di fuori del campo di applicazione della norma stessa data la natura del materiale sottoposto a prova.			
- Campionamento e preparazione provini eseguiti dalla ditta committente.			
- La Ditta committente ha richiesto di non effettuare il condizionamento prima della prova e di non operare in conformità alla norma EN 326-1/95 "Campionamento", "Provini" ed "Espressione dei risultati di prova".			
- Non è stata effettuata l'identificazione analitica del materiale sottoposto a prova.			

Table 6 CATAS procedure testing results of swelling after 24 hours of water immersion

Translation of the document

Swelling after 24 h immersion in water - CATAS internal procedure
Type of panel declared : Recycled Fiberglass panel density 1100 kg/m ³
Cutting direction : not declared
Sample dimensions : 50 x 50 mm

Test results

Sample N.	Initial Thickness mm.	Final Thickness mm	Swelling %
1	20,81	20,85	0,2
2	20,77	20,82	0,3
3	20,74	20,80	0,3
4	20,79	20,83	0,2
5	20,64	20,68	0,2
6	20,65	20,69	0,2
7	20,61	20,65	0,2
8	20,72	20,76	0,2
		Median Value	0,2
		Values range	0,0
		Variation coefficient	0,0

Excellent results have been observed under EN 317:1993 for swelling after 24 hours of panel sample immersion in water. This test measures the swelling and surface modifications following 24 hours of continuous water immersion, making it particularly relevant for materials and products intended outdoor use.

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RAPPORTO DI PROVA 349711 / 2 Revisione: 0 Ricevimento campione: 23/05/23 Esecuzione prova: 01/06/23 Emissione documento: 09/06/23 Denominaz.campione: PANNELLO RECOMPLAX D'ECOF 1100 KGM3		GEES RECYCLING S.R.L. VIA MONTE COLOMBERA 22 33081 AMANO (PN) ITALIA																	
Piccola fiamma su una sola faccia UNI 8457:2010																			
Preparazione delle provette: senza supporto incombustibile Tempo di contatto con la fiamma pilota: 30 s																			
Risultati della prova																			
Provetta n°	Tempo di post-combustione				Tempo di post-irrandescenza				Zona danneggiata				Gocciolamento				Rottura del filo di cotone		
	1° serie		2° serie		1° serie		2° serie		1° serie		2° serie		1° serie		2° serie		1° ser.	2° ser.	
	s	liv.	s	liv.	s	liv.	s	liv.	mm	liv.	mm	liv.	Riev.	liv.	Riev.	liv.	Riev.	liv.	
1	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
2	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
3	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
4	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
5	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
6	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
7	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
8	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
9	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
10	0	1			0	1			35	1			assente	1				no	
Livello attribuito	1				1				1				1						
Fattore moltiplic.	2				1				2				1						
Totale parziale	2				1				2				1						
Osservazioni ed fenomeni particolari / Provette n° 1 - 2 - 3 - 4 e 5: ricavate in direzione longitudinale. Provette n° 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 e 10: ricavate in direzione trasversale.															TOTALE CATEGORIA		6		
																	1		

Il presente rapporto di prova fa parte di un file in formato PDF a disposizione con firma digitale di Franco Bulian.

Il Direttore
Dott. Franco Bulian

La denominazione e l'eventuale descrizione del campione sono dichiarate dal cliente; il CATAS non s'impiega a verificarne la veridicità. I risultati riportati sul rapporto di prova si riferiscono solo al campione provato. Aggiunte, omissioni o alterazioni non sono ammesse. Il rapporto di prova non può essere riprodotto parzialmente. Se non diversamente previsto da norme, specifiche tecniche o accordi con il cliente le eventuali dichiarazioni di conformità formulate dal CATAS si basano sul confronto dei risultati ed i valori di riferimento senza considerare l'intervallo di confidenza della misura. Salvo diversa indicazione, il campionamento è stato effettuato dal cliente in tal caso i risultati ottenuti si riferiscono al campione e non al risultato.

Table 7 CATAS testing of small flame in one face only – UNI 8457:2010

The produced panels were tested for fire exposure according to the Italian official construction norms UNI EN 8457:2010 have demonstrated exceptional fire retardant properties. Additionally, materials sourced from the MAELSTROM project achieve Class 1, similar to the standard panels derived from non-marine litter made by Gees Recycling.

7. Maelstrom developed product and marketable items

7.1 Standard panels

Standard panels made with Maelstrom are really suitable for outdoor furniture and applications, standing the excellent resistance to weather and liquids.

Figure 36 Standard panels

Panels are available in a standard size of 2500 x 1240 mm and thicknesses ranging from 8 to 30 mm, offered in two versions:

- **D'Ecò Maelstrom XL Magnum:** This version features large grains and particles that retain the original colors of marine litter, particularly from EOL abandoned boats.
- **D'Ecò Maelstrom S:** This variant has a grain and appearance similar to our traditional product.

Figure 37 Left): Ecò Maelstrom XL-Magnum; right:) D'Ecò Maelstrom S

D'Ecò Magnum panels will not feature a standard color card, as their appearance is uniquely determined by the fragments of boats and other marine litter (ML) used in each production batch. This results in an ever-changing, "true life" aesthetic that visually embodies the process and concept behind the product.

The production process is identical for both materials. Maelstrom S was developed to offer a marine litter-sourced recycled panel with a consistent appearance and the option to select colors, similar to GEES's standard D'Eco recycling panels.

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Color card for non-Magnum types is the same of the D'Ecò panels

Color card **Recomplax® d'ecò** indoor/outdoor

Figure 38 Color card D'Ecò Panels.

7.2 Finished products ready for market

Here below you may find examples of Marketable Refined Products from GEES:
project

**Benches , solid and too heavy
to be carried away**

Flower container

Figure 39 Urban outdoor furniture – Bench and flower containers realized and placed in Genova.

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production

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- Synergies with REFRESH project

- Inalterable
- Fully recycled composites
- Cost competitive
- Fully Green Public Procurement compliant

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 40 Urban outdoor furniture – Flower Container (digitally generated picture).

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production

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- A4 Brochure for Tables
- Benches
- Flowerpots and Planters with Maelstrom scheme on back

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 41 Urban outdoor furniture.

- Standard line of urban-outdoor furniture in production

- A4 Brochure with Maelstrom scheme on back

Figure 42 Urban outdoor furniture

7.3 Future developments

Components for Floating Piers: Plans are underway to expand our product range to include components specifically designed for constructing floating piers, leveraging our advanced materials technology.

Figure 43 Floating piers (digitally generated picture).

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Floating piers are typically constructed from reinforced concrete or plastic, often featuring walkways made of steel or wood. Maelstrom panels are ideal for this application, as they are impervious to water and highly resistant to UV damage.

8. Lessons learnt from Treating Hard-to-Recycle Plastics Derived from Marine Litter

We can draw some conclusions from the initial preparation and sorting of marine litter through to the challenges of dealing with organic and inorganic contaminants, and the final stages of cleaning and recycling, our experiences have provided valuable insights. Below, we list the key lessons learned and results achieved that have emerged from managing and recycling marine litter collected during the implementation of MAELSTROM project via advanced mechanical recycling at GEES industrial processing plant.

1. Marine Litter Feedstock Preparation

- **Nets with Low Organic Residue:** While these nets contain minimal organic residues, they require special attention during the shredding process. Traditional double-shaft shredders are unsuitable as the nets can tangle around the shafts, potentially blocking even high-powered machines.
- **Organic Content in Nets:** The organic content, or biomass, of these nets is relatively low, posing minor issues in the recycling process.
- **Handling of Large Ropes:** The presence of large ropes necessitates additional manual handling. However, this can be mitigated by employing a large monorotor shredder, which is more effective for such materials.

Figure 44 Nets debris

- **Organic contamination of floaters:** The contamination of HDPE floaters significantly hinders their recyclability. As evident from the image, the mass of mussels and other seashells can equal the weight of the floater itself. The presence of salt requires pre-treatment, as salt and water in the extrusion process can transform into HCL, leading to severe corrosion and the release of toxic gases. Therefore, it is necessary to separate the marine biomass from the plastic before recycling.

Figure 45 Removal of a buoy - VLPF clean-up

- **Cleaning of Collected Marine Litter:** The collected marine litter requires thorough cleaning to remove mud, sand, and salt. This is essential not only for determining the composition—whether it's plastic, metal, composite, or mixed—but also for preparing it for further processing.
- **Operational Requirements:** The cleaning operation should be conducted in a paved area equipped with facilities for collecting water and other liquids for treatment. At the GEES plant, all waste water is collected and treated by the industrial depurator.

Figure 46 Cleaning of collected marine litter

2. Sorting and Separation

FRP+ Wood

Figures 71, FRP and Wood

FRP

Metal

This operation is lengthy and labor-intensive, and currently, it cannot be fully automated, necessitating the use of manual labor. Particularly for boat parts and fragments, straightforward techniques like the use of magnets are essential to detect

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hidden metal reinforcements completely encased in fiberglass that must be separated from the remaining litter.

- **Handling Fiberglass-Wood Components:** A specific protocol needs to be established for handling fiberglass-wood parts to ensure compliance with environmental regulations. For our authorization, the wood content in the plastic waste must remain below 25%.
- **Innovation in Recycling Technologies:** With the increasing amounts of marine litter and materials from end-of-life (EOL) boats, there is an urgent need to develop and implement innovative, automated solutions to improve processing efficiency.

3. Recycling operations

The planned recycling operations have successfully demonstrated the practical feasibility of transforming challenging marine litter feedstock into valuable materials and products:

- By adopting the appropriate processing parameters and implementing some modifications, the GEES Recycling mechanical recycling system achieved favorable results.
- Despite the mixed, varied, and contaminated nature of ML waste, it was possible to process it to yield predictable and repeatable outcomes and products.
- The energy and environmental impacts were comparable to those of recycling other types of waste managed by GEES.
- The project produced materials from waste that, without recycling, would either deteriorate over a long period in the environment or require costly and complex disposal in landfills.
- The quality of the materials obtained is consistently comparable to that of commonly used products.
- The system demonstrated comprehensive traceability from the ML source location to the refined product in the market.

9. Valorization of Organic Biomass and Marine Litter in Marine Ecosystems

Introduction

The increasing concern over marine ecosystem degradation, largely due to waste accumulation and the underutilization of organic biomass residues, underscores the need for innovative valorization strategies. This task of the MAELSTROM project explores the potential benefits of valorizing organic biomass, specifically from marine sources like shell waste and blue crab residues, alongside marine litter (i.e. plastic litter collected from marine ecosystems). By focusing on the ecological and industrial importance of recycling and valorizing the mentioned materials, the chapter advocates for blending organic biomass with marine litter to transform waste into valuable products, contributing to both environmental sustainability and economic opportunities.

9.1 Marine Litter and Organic Biomass from Marine Ecosystems

Marine litter, particularly plastics, is one of the most pressing global environmental issues. Hard-to-recycle plastics, including those from abandoned fishing gear, ropes, and other waste materials found in the sea, pose significant challenges. Projects like the VLPF Ghost Boat Programme have made strides in tackling these problems by processing abandoned fiberglass boats and transforming the recovered plastics into usable products, such as outdoor urban furniture.

The blending of these materials with organic biomass, especially through mechanical treatments and the development of composite prototypes, has opened new avenues for sustainable material creation. Research demonstrates that combining HDPE (high-density polyethylene) with organic fillers, such as shell waste of CBBs from crustaceous wastes (i.e. Blue Crabs), can produce durable, cost-effective, and eco-friendly materials. These materials not only reduce the environmental footprint of plastic production but also offer alternatives to traditional petrochemical-based products.

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More in depth, organic biomass in marine environments, such as shell waste and residues from species like blue crabs, represents a significant resource that is underutilized so far. The shells, primarily composed of calcium carbonate, and crab residues, rich in chitin and other biologically valuable compounds, can be processed into CBBs - Chemical Building Blocks for various industries. The case of blue crab residues, particularly prevalent in the Venice Lagoon and Mediterranean regions, illustrates how these organic materials, initially considered a threat to local ecosystems, can be repurposed for innovative applications. Thanks to the strong synergy created among partners GESS, VLPF, ISDI and the respective stakeholders, like Biochica start up and University of Trento, a set of potential blending and prototypes implementation has been implemented.

A promising blending and creation of new biomaterial has been possible through the blending of specific *OCBBs* - *Organic Chemical Building Blocks* from Blue Crabs and specific marine litter (i.e. HDPE). Biochica's work in extracting and blending chitin/chitosan and carbonate salts, with the activities of blending carried out by the University of Trento provides a model for turning environmental challenges into marketable solutions, creating opportunities for industries reliant on biodegradable polymers and biomaterial applications. Such valorization processes are not only aligned with circular economy principles but also highlight the synergy between environmental conservation and technological innovation.

9.2 Blending Organic Biomass and Marine Litter: A Sustainable Solution

The blending of marine litter, particularly plastic waste, with organic biomass presents a unique opportunity to address both environmental waste and resource scarcity. Through innovative processes developed by collaborations between GEES, VLPF and ISDI, with stakeholders Biochica, and UniTN, prototypes of blended materials have demonstrated considerable potential.

By integrating materials like blue crab chitosan with marine-derived plastics, new Biocomposites are created, offering improved mechanical properties while maintaining eco-friendly credentials

VLPF and ISDI monitored marine biomass in terms of quality and quantity of the most abundant aquatic residues during the months June 2023 – September 2023 located in the Venice lagoon during the cleaning up actions

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The further collaboration with Biochica Start up, let to plan the promising extraction through sustainable condition of the key polymers with potential application into the new biomaterial, (Fig.74).

T6.4 Hard to recycle plastics and organic wastes: Partners (GEES - ISDI – VLPF), Stakeholders (BIOCHICA – UniTN)

1° Step: Organic Biomass waste valorization : ISDI , VLPF, Biochica Start Up

Figure 47 Valorization of Organic Biomass: A Sustainable Approach (Biochica, VLPF and ISDI), 2024

The collaboration with UniTN let to better investigate the compatibility between organic marine biomass and selected marine litter. Thus, several experimental texts about technical extraction of biopolymers (carried out by Biochica) and blending with selected marine litter (carried out by UniTn) at specific technical conditions, let to obtain the first prototypes of the novel biomaterial reaching the blending of organic material up to 60% of the plastic waste, with further increasing of biodegradation of novel biomaterial.

Several experimental texts about blending of the selected waste materials have been implemented at difference ratio between selected HDPE with fillers Chitin/Chitosan and Carbonate salts, (Fig.75) and (Fig.76).

T6.4 Hard to recycle plastics and organic wastes: Partners (GEES - ISDI – VLPF), Stakeholders (BIOCHICA – UniTN)

2° Step: Valorization of Marine Litter, Plastic and Organic Biomass: Blending and Prototype (GEES, UNITN, Biochica)

Figure 48 Valorization of Marine Litter and Marine Biomass: HDPE and Chitin Blending (Biochica and UniTN, Stakeholder of the MAELSTROM project, 2024)

Figure 49 Valorization of Marine Litter and Marine Biomass: HDPE and Chitin Blending for Sustainable Prototypes (Biochica and UniTN, Stakeholder of the MAELSTROM project, 2024)

Experimental text and further investigations on HDPE blends showed that incorporating organic fillers can enhance mechanical properties such as elastic modulus, though there are challenges regarding the adhesion between fillers and selected HDPE, (Fig. 77), Fig. (78). The first results shows that HDPE without blending is a material that behaves under tensile stress. It reaches a certain point of strain where the stress increases non-linearly before breaking. HDPE exhibits elastic behavior up to a certain strain before undergoing plastic deformation, typical of many thermoplastics (Fig. 77).

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When the selected HDPE is blended with Chitin/Chitosan and carbonate salts, the **Elastic modulus (stiffness)** increases with higher chitin content. The HDPE-Chitin composites show improved stiffness, meaning the material becomes more rigid as more chitin is added (Fig. 77).

Also, **Yield stress (σ_y)** changes with chitin content. The yield strength generally increases, meaning the material can withstand more stress before deforming plastically.

However, the **elongation at break (ϵ_B)**, which represents the material's ductility or ability to stretch before breaking, tends to decrease with higher chitin content. This means the material becomes less flexible as more chitin is introduced.

Furthermore, the images from a scanning electron microscope (SEM) point out how the fracture surface of a material composed of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) blended with fillers, (chitin/chitosan and carbonate salts) shows issues with adhesion between the HDPE matrix and the filler material, due to the greater dimensions of particle sizes of filler (Fig.78).

Future work will focus on improving filler compatibility, and adhesion to maximize both performance and sustainability with different marine litters.

At last, first results highlight:

- **Higher chitin content** in the composite increases stiffness and strength but reduces flexibility.
- The blend of HDPE and chitin creates a material that is stronger and more rigid, making it suitable for applications requiring higher mechanical strength. However, the trade-off is a loss of ductility, so the material becomes more brittle at higher chitin percentages.

This mechanical behavior aligns with the goal of creating more sustainable, Biocomposite materials from marine litter and organic waste, showing how the properties of these blends can be tuned for specific applications.

Future research activities will be carried out by Biochica and UniTN after the end of the project and will focus on improving filler compatibility to maximize both performance and sustainability.

T6.4 Hard to recycle plastics and organic wastes: Partners (GEES - ISDI – VLPF), Stakeholders (BIOCHICA – UniTN)

2° Step: Valorization of Marine Litter, Plastic and Organic Biomass: Blending and Prototype (GEES, UNITN, Biochica)

Mechanical properties

Figure 50 Mechanical Properties of the prototypes, (Data delivered by UniTN and Biochica, 2024)

Figure 51 Scanning electron microscope observation of the fracture surface of HDPE_60% Chitin/Chitosan and Carbonate Salts, (Data delivered by UniTN and Biochica, 2024)

This first investigation and experimental texts highlight the circular nature of the proposed solution—marine litter is repurposed into valuable products, reducing the burden on ecosystems while providing alternatives for industries in need of sustainable materials.

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9.3 Prototyping and Potential Applications

The stakeholders (Biochica and UniTn) are working to improve the technical properties of the mentioned biomaterial with the aim of reaching credible patents and scientific publications.

Continuous improvement and further experimental and stress-tests on the technical properties of the novel biomaterial are still necessary before to better understand its promising applications as well as the potential markets.

The prototypes developed as part of these valorization efforts could include urban outdoor furniture such as benches, tables, and planters made from blended composites of marine litter and organic biomass, (Fig. 79-83).

Figure 52 Sustainable Biomaterials for Garden and Outdoor Furnishings

These products not only demonstrate durability and cost competitiveness but are also fully compliant with Green Public Procurement (GPP) standards, offering a sustainable alternative to conventional materials.

Within this context, GEES partner is an expert in specific market sectors, offering strong opportunities to accelerate the time to further develop, up from TRL 5 to 9.

Moreover, each product would be designed to be fully traceable, with tags or QR codes that could allow consumers to track the origin of the recycled materials used in their production. This transparency would enhance the environmental credibility of the products, as well as support consumer engagement with sustainability.

Conclusion

The valorization of organic biomass from marine ecosystems, in combination with the recycling of marine litter, represents a transformative approach to addressing two major environmental challenges simultaneously. By creating value from waste, this method offers sustainable solutions that benefit both the environment and the economy. The collaboration between stakeholders such as Biochica, UniTN, and MAELSTROM Partners like VLPF, ISDI and GEES demonstrated the potential for cross-sector innovation, setting the stage for future advancements in green technology and

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materials science, through the valorization of the specific roles of the members within an EU Project.

Continued research and development in this field, particularly in improving material compatibility and expanding the range of prototypes after the end of the project, will be crucial to scaling these efforts and maximizing their impact on both a regional and European scale.

